

INTERFACIAL TENSION AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART II

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The complexing tendency of various anions, e.g., halides, thiosulphate, nitrate, nitrite, acetate, sulphate, chlorate and perchlorate, when added to zinc chloride, nitrate and sulphate, has been examined. Also, such a tendency of magnesium, lead and zinc chlorides with different bivalent chlorides and lead, zinc and beryllium nitrate with different nitrates is reported.

Electrostatic attractions, such as ion dipole ones, are responsible for the existence of complexes formed between different metal salts in aqueous solution. The energy changes involved in such complex formation must correspond to the order of the strength of the unstable hydrogen bond of liquids like *n*-butyl or isoamyl acetate. This hydrogen bond is primarily electrostatic in character, and hence, must be susceptible to such energy changes. As a consequence, complexing between different ionic species or dipoles in aqueous solution should be also amenable to the study of interfacial tension measurements of such solutions against such H-bonded liquids. With this view, the complex formation between aqueous zinc chloride, nitrate, sulphate, on one hand and other electrolytes, viz., potassium bromide, iodide, sulphate, nitrate, nitrite, chlorate, perchlorate, sodium acetate and thiosulphate on the other hand, has now been investigated.

In the previous work (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 957), the tendency among various bivalent metal chlorides and nitrates for complex formation has already been reported. This work includes chlorides of magnesium, zinc and lead and nitrates of lead, zinc and beryllium for such purpose.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The salts used were of standard quality. The interfacial tension values of a series of mixed aqueous salt solutions (prepared from each stock solution) against isoamyl or *n*-butyl acetate, measured by the method previously described (*loc. cit.*), when plotted against the volume of the variant A, indicate peaks corresponding to complex formation. The compositions of these complexes are shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
[Conc. M/100, each]

[a = A.4B, b = A.3B, c = A.2B, d = 2A.3B, e = A.B, f = 3A.2B, g = 2A.B]								
Salt B.	Peaks corresp. to Salt A : ZnCl ₂ .	Salt B	Peaks	Salt B	Peaks.	Salt A.	Salt B	Peaks.
		Salt A : Zn(NO ₃) ₂ .		Salt A : ZnSO ₄ .				
KBr	a, b, c, d, e, f, g	CH ₃ COONa	c, e, g	KNO ₃	c, e, g	ZnCl ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	c, e, g
KI	a, b, c, d, e, f, g	KBr	c, e, g	CH ₃ COONa	c, e, g	ZnCl ₂	ZnSO ₄	c, e, g
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄	a, b, c, d, e, f, g	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄	c, e, g	KBr	c, e, g	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	ZnSO ₄	c, e, g
KNO ₃	c, e, g	K ₂ SO ₄	c, e, g	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	c, e, g			
KNO ₂	c, e, g	KClO ₃	c, e, g	KClO ₃	c, e, g			
CH ₃ COONa	c, e, g	KClO ₄	c, e, g	KClO ₄	c, e, g			
K ₂ SO ₄	c, e, g							
KClO ₃	c, e, g							
KClO ₄	c, e, g							

TABLE II

[a = A.4B, b = A.3B, c = A.2B, d = A.B, e = 2A.B, f = 3A.B, g = 4A.B]			
Conc. (M/)	Salt A.	Salt B.	Peaks correspond to
80	CuCl ₂	MgCl ₂	c, d, e
80	CoCl ₂	MgCl ₂	c, d, e
80	NiCl ₂	MgCl ₂	c, d, e
80	PbCl ₂	MgCl ₂	-, d, e
80	PbCl ₂	CuCl ₂	-, d, e
80	PbCl ₂	CoCl ₂	-, d, e
80	PbCl ₂	NiCl ₂	-, d, e
80	MgCl ₂	ZnCl ₂	c, d, -
80	MgCl ₂	BaCl ₂	c, d, -
80	MgCl ₂	CdCl ₂	c, d, -
80	PbCl ₂	CdCl ₂	c, d,
80	PbCl ₂	ZnCl ₂	c, d, -
80	PbCl ₂	CaCl ₂	c, d, -
80	ZnCl ₂	CdCl ₂	-, d, e
80	ZnCl ₂	CoCl ₂	-, d, e
80	SrCl ₂	CdCl ₂	-, d, e
80	BaCl ₂	CdCl ₂	-, d, e
80	ZnCl ₂	SrCl ₂	c, d, e
80	CaCl ₂	SrCl ₂	c, d, e
80	BaCl ₂	ZnCl ₂	c, d, e
80	BaCl ₂	CaCl ₂	c, d, e
30	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d
30	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Co(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, -, -, g
30	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, -, -, g
30	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, -, -, g
40	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Mg(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, -
40	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
30	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, -
40	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-, -, c, d, e, -, g
30	Co(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	a, -, c, d, e, -, g
30	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-, -, c, d, e, -, g
50	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-, -, c, d, e, -, g
40	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-, -, c, d, e, -, g
50	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, -, -, -
100	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, -, -, -
100	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Co(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Cu(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Mg(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g
100	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	Be(NO ₃) ₂	a, b, c, d, e, f, g

It appears that the complexing capacity of different anions, added to zinc salt, depends not only on the nature of these anions but also on the nature of anion of the zinc salt (vide Table I). The complexes formed between zinc chloride and halides-thiosulphate, nitrate-nitrite-acetate, sulphate, and chlorate are (a, b, c, d, e, f, g), (c, e, g), (c, e) and (e) respectively. Hence, the order of the complexing capacity of these anions with zinc chloride is: halide = $S_2O_3^{2-} > NO_3^- = NO_2^- = \text{acetate} > SO_4^{2-} > ClO_3^-$. With zinc nitrate, however, this order is: acetate $>$ halide = $S_2O_3^{2-} = SO_4^{2-} > ClO_3^-$ and with zinc sulphate it is: $NO_3^- = \text{acetate} >$ halide = $S_2O_3^{2-} > ClO_3^-$. The perchlorate ion does not show any such tendency, indicating the absence of co-ordinating reactions in perchlorate solutions which are commonly used when no complexing is desired. Among zinc salts the degree of complexing observed in mixed solutions of zinc chloride and nitrate is greater than that with zinc nitrate-sulphate or zinc sulphate-chloride solutions.

As regards the complexing capacity of different cations among metal chlorides, copper, cobalt, nickel and magnesium cations have the same degree of complexing tendency among themselves (c, d, e). Similar behaviour is also observed among zinc, calcium barium and strontium cations. However, among the several cations, the degree of complexing would be in the order: $Cu = Co = Ni = Mg > Pb > Cd > Zn = Sr = Ba = Ca$.

Among metal nitrates, it may be observed that lead cation has less complexing tendency than Cd in cadmium-lead pair (a, b, c, d), slightly greater than copper, cobalt or nickel ion (a, c, d, g) in lead-cobalt, copper, or nickel pair, where (c) is evident, but (e) is absent, greater than magnesium in lead-magnesium pair (a, c, d, e), and same as calcium, barium, strontium or zinc (a, c, d, e, g). Zinc cation has less tendency than cadmium or magnesium in cadmium-zinc (a, c, d, e) or zinc-magnesium pair, (c, d, e, g), same as copper, cobalt or nickel (a, c, d, e, g) and greater than calcium, barium or strontium (c, d, e, g) in barium, calcium or strontium-zinc pair. Beryllium cation indicates the same degree of complexing capacity as cadmium, copper, cobalt, nickel, magnesium, calcium, barium or strontium in the solutions of these metal nitrates mixed with beryllium nitrate. However, when lead or zinc nitrate solution is mixed with beryllium nitrate, beryllium shows less complexing capacity than lead or zinc (a, b, c, d).

The formation of these complex ions in solution is probably dependent upon ion-dipole attractions. The existence of dipoles, whether sulphates, chlorides or nitrates etc., thus permits apparently neutral molecules to attract ions and other such molecular species and results in combinations, which although apparently stoichiometric, are not related to electron exchange or sharing. Cations, like beryllium with comparatively small size and high nuclear charge, serve as best centres of co-ordination, as anions would be highly polarised by them. McBain and Rysselburge (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 3009) have shown that complex ions are formed by the combination of ordinary undissociated molecules with ions, when sulphate ions are added to bivalent sulphates. It has been further indicated that these complex anions cannot be considered negligible in dilute solutions also. McBain *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1930, **52**, 2336) have drawn the general conclusion that strong electrolytes form undissociated molecules and complex anions.

They differ only in degree from such an extreme case as that of cadmium iodide. Electrolytes would all seem to fall within a triangle, whose corners represent extreme dissociation, extremely weak electrolytes and complete formation of complex ions respectively.

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